

Effect of laser-assisted surface modification of NdFeB permanent magnets applicable in high-demand working environment

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Abstract: This article focuses on research on innovative coatings for permanent magnets used in electrical machines, basing on Ti and ZrO₂ powders. The coatings provide a permanent chemical bond and have been prepared by applying chemical powders with the help of TRUMPF TruLaser Robot 5020 in a continuous manner. Comprehensive tests of the prepared samples, like scanning electron microscopy (SEM), were carried out to analyze surface quality, porosity, homogeneity, and the possible presence of surface defects. Additionally, the FEM field analysis were performed using the ANSYS Maxwell software which allowed to determine magnetic field distribution for NdFeB magnets. Verification of software calculations was carried out according to the different environment conditions like high temperature, water, sea water or soil. The authors performed studies of the Magnetic flux density changes for selected magnets without and with selected coatings. Obtained results showed that newly developed, industrial scale laser-assisted method for Neodymium magnets modifications constitutes an ecofriendly, promising way to prepare fine elements for modern machines construction.

Keywords: permanent magnets, innovative coatings, PM machines, laser modification

1. Introduction

The rapid progress in the field of new technologies, combined with the growing awareness of society in the context of caring for environmental quality, results in the development of modern solutions for more efficient energy management and makes it one of the priority areas of modern science. The development of permanent magnets with enhanced physicochemical resistance will significantly contribute to the development of many different scientific disciplines, which may result in previously unknown construction solutions using magnetic materials.

Conducting basic research on a completely new class of such materials may make it possible to propose a novel approach to the issue of domestic wind turbines thereby providing previously unknown tools to produce green energy. The development of a new class of permanent magnets in the long term may allow the development of a completely new method of improving the operation of motors and generators, since the efficiency of permanent magnet machines is largely related to the value of the magnetic induction produced by the magnets influence directly on values of induced voltages and thus its efficiency. A very good knowledge of the

properties of magnets at both theoretical and experimental levels is essential from the point of view of designing electric machines.

The commonly used permanent magnets have a wide range of applications, ranging from electrical machines, everyday appliances to medical solutions. Depending on the method of production and the materials used, magnets differ not only in their mechanical parameters, but especially in their magnetic properties. The strongest permanent magnets are the alloy of Neodymium, Iron and Boron and belong to rare earth magnets [2]. Their ubiquity has led to their production in various shapes, sizes and axes of magnetization. Unfortunately, because of their prone to crushing, sensitivity to external conditions it is impossible to implement them in demanding environmental conditions. This problem requires a corrosion protection, thereby to cover magnets with adequate coatings [3,4].

Therefore, in order to maintain favorable magnetic properties, it is fundamental to coat the magnets with appropriate coatings with well-defined characteristics. There are many commonly used coating materials like among others: Ni-Cu-Ni, Gold, Zinc, Teflon, Rubber, Chrome or Titanium Nitride (TiN) [5-8]. Despite the development of many methods of surface modification of such materials, it has still not been possible to develop such a solution that would allow to maintain satisfactory magnetic properties with simultaneous improvement of thermal, chemical and mechanical resistance. Currently, most common permanent magnets functionalization is based on electrochemical processes [8]. Nowadays, there are multiple methods of coating, however most of them gives satisfactory levels of physicochemical characteristics and properties repeatability only on a laboratory scale [9-11]. One of the most promising ways to improve materials overall performance is laser-assisted treatment since it enables fast, strictly controlled, and precise surface modification [12].

Laser cladding and alloying is an advanced manufacturing method used for surface modification of metallic materials in the modern industries. The cladding process is surface modification technique, which is used for deposition of a thick layer of advanced materials on the surface of conventional materials to improve the surface properties like, wear resistance, hardness, oxidation resistance, corrosion resistance and heat resistance. The advanced materials generally used for cladding operations are transition metals, alloys, ceramics, composites, nanomaterials, rare earth oxides. Laser cladding is the most widely used coating technique because of its attractive properties such as good metallurgical bonding between coating and the substrate, less distortion, narrow heat affected zone, high solidification, and cooling rate. The various process parameters which affect the quality of laser clad layer or alloyed layer are laser power, scanning speed, laser spot diameter, inert gas flow rate and frequency of the laser beam. For cladding and alloying purposes various materials are used: transition metals, alloys, ceramics, composites and rare earth oxides. The various metallic materials which are used for cladding are Al, Ti, Si, Co, Cr, Fe, Zn, Zr, Ni, and Cu [13-17].

The processes which are described here for surface modification of metal alloys are laser surface cladding and laser surface alloying [18]. These processes are used separately for improvement in surface properties and tribological properties of various alloys. The laser cladding and alloying can be divided into five types, namely: pre-placed powder technique, powder injection method, coaxial powder feeding method, wire feed method and paste form feeding [19].

In pre-placed powder technique, the coating powders were mixed properly in polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), which acts as a binder. After mixing, the paste is placed uniformly on the surface of substrate material to get a uniform thickness of pre-coated layer. The pre-coated layer should be dried properly before application of a laser heat source for melting the powder. After that laser heat source is applied vertically on the horizontally placed pre-coated substrate surface. The coated layer and the substrate material forms a good metallurgical bond with each other [20]. In the powder injection method for surface cladding on magnesium alloys mixed powders are fed through the side nozzle at the laser-metal interaction zone. After melting and solidification, a coated surface layer is obtained. Simultaneously the inert gas is supplied through the side for protection against the atmospheric contamination. Generally, argon gas is used for shielding purposes [21-22]. In this process the coating powder is supplied coaxially along the laser beam through a coaxial nozzle. First, the powder mixture falls on the surface of the substrate at the interaction zone. After that laser heat source is applied to melt the powder. After melting and solidification, a coated layer forms on the surface of magnesium alloy. It is a highly efficient process among all the laser cladding and alloying processes [23-24].

In wire feed method the feedstock is used in the form of wire. In this method wire of coating material is supplied by side at some angle to the laser wire interaction spot. Only metal or alloy coatings can be performed by this process. Only wires of transition metal or alloy are generally found in the market. The composite coating cannot be done by wire feed technique because wires of composite are not generally found in the market [25].

During paste form feeding process the coating material is mixed with some binder so that it can form a paste. The coating material is supplied in the form of paste through the side nozzle. When paste falls on the surface of the coating zone then the laser beam heats vertically to the interaction zone and it melts the powder paste. After melting and solidification, a coated layer forms on the substrate surface [26].

Laser-assisted modification can be considered as environment-friendly since it strongly reduces number of wastes generated during production processes, enables leftover powders recovery, helps to save energy, and does not emit harmful gases or dusts. Another important property is possibility of process automatization and real-time control. Therefore, currently industrial manufacturing of metal-based parts dedicated to applications which require fine details such as tools for green energy production or electric cars highly relies on laser workstations [27-33].

The authors attempted to develop novel coatings for neodymium (NdFeB) magnets using modern laser techniques based on the use of titanium and zirconium dioxide as the main modifying factors and the analysis of physicochemical properties to confirm the validity of the research hypothesis. The selection of chemicals and the method of surface modification envisioned for implementation was based on an analysis of the requirements for modern machines using permanent magnets, including applications in electric machines working with renewable energy sources, the marine industry, and mining.

Hence, the neodymium magnets have been coated with Ti and ZrO_2 . For coatings application the authors used TRUMPF TruLaser Robot 5020 which allowed to obtain accurate surface coatings. The use of robotic station to apply powders is increasingly replacing manual coating methods due to the increase in coating precision required.

Titanium, which is characterized by high mechanical strength and is, above all, highly resistant to corrosion, including, importantly, to the effects of seawater and chlorine, while zirconium is known of its superior high temperature resistance. Moreover, it is also fire-resistant, which significantly increases the usefulness of magnet machines in the metallurgical or mining industries. Additionally, ZrO_2 is chemically stable and inert thus provide good protection from harsh environmental factors, especially under high-humidity areas.

The aim of this research was to perform superficial modification of neodymium magnets to increase their resistance to environmental factors resulting in potential performance and durability enhancement. The use of robotized workstation enabled development of industrial-scale coating technology, which is extremely important in the case of potential application in the field of electrical machines production, especially for green energy generation.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Materials

Isopropanol was purchased from SigmaAldrich. ZrO_2 powder in a form of microgranules (Fig. 1 (a)) was purchased from Alchem Sp. z o. o., Ti powder (spongy titanium) was purchased from Ireneusz Katarzyński Selkat (Fig. 1 (b)). Sea water for aging study was obtained from Mediterranean Sea. Soil was collected from Małopolskie voivodeship. For the experiments, commercial NdFeB magnets without any coating and with standard for electric machines Ni-Cu-Ni coating (thickness: 8 - 30 μm , usually 10 - 15 μm) were applied. Laser-assisted modification was performed using uncoated magnets. The authors selected NdFeB magnets in two sizes in the shape of a cuboid, both N38 type, with the following dimensions: 40x18x10 mm and 20x10x5 mm. The magnetic parameters of N38 PM magnets are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Parameters of permanent magnets NdFeB type N38 [product datasheet]

Parameter	Value
magnet remanence B_r	1,21 - 1,25 [T]
magnet coercivity H_{cB}	min. 899 [kA/m]
magnet coercivity H_{cJ}	min. 955 [kA/m]
magnetic energy density (BH) _{max}	286 - 302 [kJ/m ³]

Fig. 1. SEM images of the powders used for coating preparation: (a) – ZrO₂; (b) – Ti

2.2. Coating preparation

The coatings were prepared using industrial-scale workstation composed of KUKA KR30 HA robot, three-stream head for coating metal powders, metal powder feeder, TRUMPF TruDisk 4002 disk laser with a rated power of 4000W, light wavelength of 1030 nm and beam divergence of 8 mm·rad, and instrumentation. Each time, magnet surface was pre-treated with isopropanol to remove dirt and dust to provide uniform area for coating. Surface modification was performed via cladding process with a scan speed of 240 mm/min and powder feed rate 1 g/min. As a shield gas Ar was applied (flow rate 20l/min) and as a carrier gas He was used (4l/min). Each time different set of parameters was applied (Table 2).

Table 2. Modification parameters

Sample number	Powder type	Power [W]	Power density [W/mm ²]	Specific energy [kJ]
1	Ti	100	59.54	19289.74
2	Ti	150	89.31	28934.61
3	Ti	175	104.19	33757.04
4	Ti	200	119.07	38579.48
5	ZrO ₂	100	59.54	19289.74
6	ZrO ₂	150	89.31	28934.61
7	ZrO ₂	175	104.19	33757.04
8	ZrO ₂	200	119.07	38579.48

The environmental tests were performed using climate chamber simulating one year period. Realtime Ambient Shelf Temperature (TRT) was 23°C. Accelerated Aging Temperature (TAA) was 55 °C. Chamber Conditioning Time was 40 days. Thermal stability was investigated using

chamber with settled temperature 180 °C. To verify correlation between temperature and magnetic properties, magnetic flux density was measured in fixed time intervals (every 5 minutes).

2.3. Morphology study

Microphotographs of the samples were obtained using HR-SEM/EDS scanning electron microscope Tescan. No sample sputtering was performed. Elemental composition of the samples was investigated using Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy SEM/EDS. For roughness evaluation Fiji J Image software was used.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Field model

Due to the different form of the materials and incomplete documentation on their parameters, actual laboratory tests were necessary for the raw and coated magnet samples, which will enable verification of the magnetostatic analysis. The field analysis allows to illustrate the whole Magnetic field distribution not only in one or few points as in the case of experimental tests.

One of the most important indicators according to the usage of permanent magnets in electric machines is Magnetic flux density [1,2]. In order to estimate flux density distribution from selected PM in 20°C, the field analyses were made with the usage of ANSYS Maxwell software. The FEM (Finite Element Method) simulation refers to the magnet without coating as the basic sample, for two magnet sizes: 10x20x5 mm and 40x18x10 mm. Figure 2 illustrates the Magnetic flux density distribution for magnet cross-section (front view) and Figure 3 presents the Magnetic flux density changes according to the distance from the middle of PM to both sides.

Fig. 2. Flux density distribution from PM on magnets on cross-section and surroundings (front view): (a) – 20x10x5 mm; (b) – 40x18x10 mm

Fig. 3. Flux density changes for two magnet sizes: 20x10x5 and 40x18x10

The maximum Magnetic flux density values concentrate in the middle of magnets and decrease in both directions. On the edges reaches the value of 530 mT for magnet 20x10x5 mm and 520 mT for 40x18x10 mm.

3.2. Surface morphology study

Fig. 4. Coatings' preparation with TRUMPF TruLaser Robot 5020

Laser surface modification technology is an effective method to modify the material surface through melting by high intensity laser beam due to its high efficiency, no pollution, and low material consumption. After laser surface modification, the microstructure of the alloy surface is changed significantly, such as the formation of a fine dendritic grain layer without obvious porosity. Nowadays, laser surface modification, mainly including the laser surface melting, laser cladding and laser surface alloying, have been extensively applied in surface engineering which clearly confirms the highest importance of this issue in the scientific field. Among these techniques, laser surface melting has attracted extensive attention to enhance the mechanical performances and corrosion resistance of various alloys due to the absence of additional alloying elements and a natural metallurgical bonding interface [13-14]. Figure 5 presents Neodymium magnet unmodified surface appearance. It may be noticed that macro-structure is quite homogeneous, nevertheless rough, uneven areas are also present. Surface microstructure is rich in microparticles of the size between 5-10 μm which can be a consequence of oxidation after exposure to air.

Fig. 5. Raw neodymium magnet surface (a) – 500x magnification; (b) – 5 000x magnification

Interestingly, it can be noticed that elements' distribution on the material is highly heterogeneous and a high amount of other rare earth metals apart from Nd like Ce are visible (Fig.6-7) which shows that elemental composition ratio differs from product data.

Fig. 6. Elemental analysis of the Nd magnet surface (a) – pristine surface; (b) – elemental mapping; (c) – Nd mapping; (d) – Fe mapping; (e) – Ce mapping; (f) – O mapping; (g) Si – mapping

Fig. 7. XRF analysis of the pristine magnet

During the research, susceptibility to degradation after exposure to various environments was verified using a climatic chamber in distilled water, sea water and soil. Fig. 8 presents SEM image of Nd magnet surface after aging study simulating 365 days period. Fig. 9 and 10 show elemental composition. As one may observe, the surface is more heterogeneous and initial stage of material degradation may be noticed such as cracks and hollows. However, structural changes can be described as moderate compared to pristine magnet (Fig. 5).

Fig. 8. Neodymium magnet surface after aging in distilled water (1 year period); (a) – 500x magnification; (b) – 5 000x magnification

From the chemical point of view, degradation also is visible since significant changes in the elements' percentage can be spotted, especially increase of Fe which can be explained by iron oxide formation causing Fe ions release from magnets.

Fig. 9. Elemental analysis of the Nd magnet surface after aging in distilled water (a) - overall surface appearance; (b) – elemental mapping; (c) Nd mapping; (d) – Fe mapping; (e) – Ce mapping; (f) – O mapping; (g) – Si mapping

Fig. 10. XRF analysis of the pristine magnet surface after aging in distilled water

In the case of Nd magnet aged in the presence of sea water rich in different inorganic salts such as NaCl and MgCl₂, major changes can be spotted resulting from high weight loss and chemical degradation. As shown in Fig. 11, compared to Fig. 5 and Fig. 9 much more uneven structures are visible as well as high heterogeneity. Again, cracks and hollows are present however much bigger compared to the sample aged in distilled water.

Fig. 11. Neodymium magnet surface after aging in sea water (1 year period); (a) – 500x magnification; (b) – 5 000x magnification

Elemental analysis (Fig. 12-13) also proves that sea water affects magnets structure in a more aggressive way since the amount of iron oxide (rust) is much higher and percentage of Fe and O content compared to other elements is the highest.

On the other hand, interesting results were collected for the magnet aged in the presence of soil. As shown in Fig. 14 no significant changes in the surface morphology can be spotted. Minor increase of heterogeneity can be observed. No signs of degradation can be distinguished. However, elemental analysis (Fig. 15-16) indicates that also in this case oxidation of iron took place. Taking all together, our results undoubtedly confirm that uncoated samples are susceptible to degradation in a humid environment. Therefore, machines which are exploited in the open-air areas cannot be constructed from parts containing unmodified Nd-magnets.

Fig. 12. Elemental analysis of the Nd magnet surface after aging in sea water (a) – overall surface appearance; (b) – elemental mapping; (c) – Nd mapping; (d) – Fe mapping; (e) – Ce mapping; (f) – O mapping; (g) – Si mapping

Fig. 13. XRF analysis of the pristine magnet surface after aging in sea water

Fig. 14. Neodymium magnet surface after aging in soil (1 year period); (a) – 500x magnification; (b) – 5 000x magnification

Fig. 15. Elemental analysis of the Nd magnet surface after aging in soil (a) – overall surface appearance; (b) – elemental mapping; (c) – Nd mapping; (d) – Fe mapping; (e) – Ce mapping; (f) – O mapping; (g) – Si mapping

Fig. 16. XRF analysis of the Nd magnet surface after aging in soil

Fig. 17 presents roughness analysis. It clearly demonstrates that aging study resulted in an increase of surface roughness due to substrate decomposition. As SEM images revealed, aging in both distilled and sea water leads to significant changes in sample structures due to degradation because of oxidation (Fig. 17 (b-c)). It can be noticed that presence of various salts accelerated the process leading to higher elements release. Fig. 17 (d) shows that pristine magnets are most stable in soil.

Figure 17. (a) – surface roughness analysis of raw Nd-based magnet; (b) – surface roughness analysis of raw Nd-based magnet after aging in distilled water; (c) – surface roughness analysis of raw Nd-based magnet after aging in sea water; (d) – surface roughness analysis of raw Nd-based magnet after aging in soil

Fig. 18 presents surface of the magnet treated with 100W. No significant changes in the overall appearance of the sample can be observed. As shown in Fig. 19 and 20, no traces of Ti can be noticed which suggests that applied power was too low to cause melting of the titanium and its

incorporation. Probably, Ti powder during feeding did not attach to the surface and was blown out with a carrier gas.

Fig. 18. Sample 1 appearance (a) – 500x magnification; (b) – 1 000x magnification

Fig. 19. Elemental analysis of Sample 5 surface (a) – overall surface appearance; (b) – elemental mapping; (c) Nd mapping; (d) – Fe mapping; (e) – Ce mapping; (f) – O mapping; (g) – Si mapping

Fig. 20 XRF analysis of the Sample 1

Fig. 21-23 present surfaces and elemental composition of magnets modified with spongy titanium powder at applied power of 150W. As shown in Fig. 21, laser treatment caused changes in magnet morphology. The surface is much smoother than pristine magnet which can be explained by melting after laser beam treatment. At the same time heterogeneity increase was observed and formation of two different phases. No pores are visible; however, few cracks can be spotted as a consequence of too high energy concentration during cladding in a one place.

Fig. 21. Sample 2 surface appearance (a) – 500x magnification; (b) – 5 000x magnification

Fig. 22 and 23 shows elemental composition of the sample surface. It can be observed that comparing to Fig. 6-7 (pristine magnet) significant changes in elemental distribution occurred. Due to the high power applied, Nd which is characterized by lower melting temperature comparing Fe created separate phase. On the other hand, Ti distribution is homogeneous, however, the amount of the powder incorporated is quite low.

Fig. 22. Elemental analysis of Sample 2 surface (a) – overall surface appearance; (b) – elemental mapping; (c) Nd mapping; (d) – Fe mapping; (e) Ce mapping; (f) – O mapping; (g) – Ti mapping

Fig. 23. XRF analysis of Sample 2

Fig. 24 reveals sample appearance after laser treatment with 175W. Again, cracks are visible. However, comparing to Sample 2, surface is smoother, and no phase separation is present. It can be noticed that grains of the spongy titanium are melted in.

Fig. 24. Sample 3 appearance (a) – 500x magnification; (b) 1 000x magnification

Fig. 25 and 26 confirms that increase in the applied power caused higher inbuilt of the titanium. Elemental distribution is more homogenous.

Fig. 25. Elemental analysis of Sample 3 surface (a) – overall surface appearance; (b) – elemental mapping; (c) – Nd mapping; (d) – Fe mapping; (e) Ce – mapping; (f) O – mapping; (g) – Ti mapping

Fig. 26. XRF analysis of Sample 3

Fig. 27 presents surface appearance after magnet treatment with power dose of 200W. It can be noted that power increase caused obtainment of more homogenous structure in a microscale compared to 150W and 175W. Modified surface is smooth. However, still some cracks are present as well as several grains. No porosity can be observed. Also, no separate phases are visible.

Fig. 27. Sample 4 appearance (a) – 500x magnification; (b) 5 000x magnification

Fig. 28-29 reveals elemental composition. It can be noticed that power increase enabled better mixing of the powder with a substrate. Elemental distribution is uniform. No separate phases can be distinguished. Nevertheless, the amount of titanium built-in the structure is still quite low (5%) and does not constitute a separate coating. Laser beam treatment caused Ti in-depth incorporation inside the material which can be explained by too high energy focus (too small beam diameter). Importantly, comparing results to Samples 1-3 it can be observed that applying higher power with no doubt causes increase of the amount of built-in powder.

Fig. 28. Elemental analysis of Sample 3 surface (a) – overall surface appearance; (b) – elemental mapping; (c) – Nd mapping; (d) – Fe mapping; (e) – Ce mapping; (f) – O mapping; (g) – Ti mapping

Fig. 29. XRF analysis of Sample 4

Fig. 30 presents results of laser beam treatment with the power of 100W. No visible changes in the morphology can be spotted compared to Fig. 5. No cracks or separate phases are present suggesting that amount of ZrO_2 introduced into the surface is negligible.

Fig. 30. Sample 5 (a) – 500x magnification; (b) 5 000x magnification

Fig. 31 and 32 confirms that power of 100W is too small to cause ZrO_2 melting and mixing with substrate. However, comparing to the magnet surface treated with the same power but different powder (Ti) in this case elements distribution is much more homogeneous. The amount of incorporated Zr is only 0.3%, yet still higher than in the case of spongy titanium.

Fig. 31. Elemental analysis of Sample 5 surface (a) – overall surface appearance; (b) – elemental mapping; (c) Nd mapping; (d) – Fe mapping; (e) Ce mapping; (f) O mapping; (g) Zr mapping

Fig. 32. XRF analysis of Sample 5

Fig. 33 demonstrates result of laser treatment with 150W. It can be noted that power increase enabled better ZrO_2 melting and mixing with the substrate, however two separate phases can be distinguished which suggests that powder did not fully integrate with magnet surface due to too low energy applied during the process.

Fig. 33. Sample 6 (a) – 500x magnification; (b) – 5 000x magnification

Fig. 34 and 35 confirm that power increase was followed by ZrO_2 incorporation. The amount of the Zr present on the surface has doubled. Nevertheless, elements distribution is highly heterogeneous and separate phases can be observed. Also, it can be noticed that zircon dioxide is more prone to mix with neodymium than iron.

Fig. 34. Elemental analysis of Sample 6 surface (a) – overall surface appearance; (b) – elemental mapping; (c) Nd mapping; (d) – Fe mapping; (e) Ce mapping; (f) O mapping; (g) Zr mapping

Fig. 35 XRF analysis of Sample 6

Fig. 36 reveals that further power increase positively affects cladding process. In this case, application of 175W caused significant change in the sample surface appearance which is now rich in ZrO_2 which created partially porous structure. Surface coverage is quite high.

Fig. 36. Sample 7 appearance (a) – 500x magnification; (b) 5 000x magnification

Fig. 37 and 38 confirm that applied parameters enabled efficient cladding of ZrO_2 . First of all, as shown in Fig. 37 Zr is a dominant element. General distribution maintained homogenous. XRF analysis revealed that magnet surface contains almost 41% of Zr and 19,1 % of O which confirms successful coating formation.

Fig. 37. Elemental analysis of Sample 7 surface: (a) – overall surface appearance; (b) – elemental mapping; (c) – Nd mapping; (d) – Fe mapping; (e) – Ce mapping; (f) – O mapping; (g) – Zr mapping

Fig. 38. XRF analysis of Sample 7

Fig. 39 shows SEM images of the Sample 8 which was obtained as a result of laser-assisted cladding at 200W power. It can be noted that although dense and compact layer was formed, multiple cracks are present as well as coating peeling process initiation is visible. In this case, applying 200W caused boiling of the material which resulted in the formation of craters/bubbles, partially in a volcano-like form as a consequence of vapors release.

Fig. 39. Sample 8 (a) – 500x magnification; (b) – 5 000x magnification

Fig. 40 and 41 show that element distribution is uniform and homogeneous. Moreover, with no doubt the surface is fully covered with ZrO_2 which was proved by Zr content of almost 62%. However, it can be noticed highly ceramic layer is formed which is susceptible to cracking and will not provide sufficient mechanical resistance of the Nd magnet.

Fig. 40. Elemental analysis of Sample 8 surface (a) – overall surface appearance; (b) – elemental mapping; (c) Nd mapping; (d) – Fe mapping; (e) – Ce mapping; (f) – O mapping; (g) – Zr mapping

Fig. 41. XRF analysis of Sample 8

It can be noticed that depending on the power and beam diameter during the cladding process, various results were obtained. However, in each case, the powder is mixed with the base material. For almost all samples, longitudinal and transverse cracks together with high surface roughness can be spotted (Fig. 42). Also, in many cases uneven distribution of elements was observed which is a typical problem during up-scaling of modification process. Overall, for samples 1-6 SEM analysis shows that the powder hasn't been fully melted down during the cladding process which can be a consequence of too low power applied. Nevertheless, since Nd-based magnets are brittle, too high dose of watts ends up with their cracking. If the power density was reduced while increasing the melted surface, the energy of the laser beam would be accumulated to a greater extent on the melting of the powder than on the melting of the surface of the genuine material. Results obtained for sample 7 and 8 modified with ZrO_2 show that proper parameters adjustment enables formation of the uniform and homogenous surface, with acceptable roughness. SEM images also showed that morphology and grain size affect powder cladding process effectiveness. Round particles with smaller diameter provide better melting and mixing with the raw surface. Noteworthy, SEM images showed that shield gas type and its flow rate was adjusted properly, since no highly porous, oxide-based structures have been formed [34-38].

Figure 42. Surface roughness analysis of (a) – sample 1; (b) – Sample 2; (c) – Sample 3; (d) – Sample 4; (e) – Sample 5; (f) – Sample 6; (g) – Sample 7; (h) –Sample 8

3.3. Magnetic flux density tests

In the end there were carried out tests to verify the field calculations, to compare the induction values close to the magnets surface, which is a key indicator here for evaluating the effectiveness of the structures created, in the context of the subsequent application of these solutions in electrical machines. The Magnetic flux density was measured above the magnet surface (according to the device's instructions), at the same distance value (5 mm) for each sample to show the character of the changes using TENMARS TM-197 (Teslameter). The Magnetic field density value 5 mm from magnet's surface, 10 mm from the magnet's middle) obtained from field analysis according to Fig. 3 is 122 mT.

Fig. 43. presents the temperature changes for no coating sample and with commercial Ni-Cu-Ni one - both 20x10x5 mm. It can be noticed that providing additional coating to increase chemical stability and durability negatively affects temperature resistance.

Fig. 43. Temperature dependence of Magnetic flux density B for no-coating magnet (blue line) and for commercial Cu-Ni-Cu magnet coating (red line)

Despite of the same dimensions and product datasheet, one can see the difference in Magnetic field density for the same magnet's material (N38) and size. The sample with commercial coating has the lower flux density value by about 7%.

The next experiments were carried out for different coating types. Table 4 shows the Magnetic flux density B for selected samples of PM: without any coating (20x10x5 mm), after aging in distilled water, sea water (sample 3) and soil, with Ti coatings (for different laser-assisted modification parameters) and with ZrO_2 coating (40x18x10mm). The tests were made directly after samples processing. The Magnetic flux density was measured above the magnet surface (according to the device's instructions), at the same distance value for each sample to show the character of the changes. Interestingly, aging studies did not cause any relevant changes in

magnetic flux density, although most of the samples underwent degradation resulting in weight loss and rust formation.

Taking under consideration fact that laser beam delivers high amount of the energy to the small area of the surface, depending on the beam diameter temperature may increase even up to thousands of degrees Celcius which leads to a decrease in magnetic flux density. However, during laser-assisted processes exposure to extremely high temperatures is relatively short, changes in magnetic properties may be reversible. Nevertheless, significant decrease in magnetic flux density was observed in all cases. Noteworthy, the higher power was applied, the higher loss of magnetic properties. Such results show that remagnetization is a necessary step in the production of magnets with enhanced via laser-assisted techniques on a large scale.

Table 4. Magnetic flux density B before remagnetization process 5 mm from the magnet's surface

Sample	Magnetic flux density B [mT]
Pristine magnet	116
Pristine magnet after aging in distilled water	111
Pristine magnet after aging in sea water	112
Pristine magnet after aging in soil	113
sample 1	63
sample 2	18
sample 3	11
sample 4	7
Sample 5	73
Sample 6	21
Sample 7	12
Sample 8	10

According to the Table 4, after laser surface modifications the Magnetic flux density for modified samples is weakened, the magnets should be again magnetized after this process.

4. Conclusions

In this article the authors presented a new surface modification strategy for permanent magnets application spectrum increase on the example of neodymium ones. The usage of modern coating technology allows to obtain accurate surface cover and permanent chemical bonds. Application of continuous laser cladding enables to proceed two different pathways of samples' modifications. The materials were further compared by scanning electron microscopy to select the best surface quality. Application of chemical powders: Ti and ZrO₂ significantly improved endurance of tested permanent magnets in several external conditions like high temperature, humidity, sea water and soil. As our study revealed, the most effective magnets modification occurred using zircon dioxide powder with 175W power which provides possibility of full surface coverage. However, our preliminary experiments showed that to obtain comparable to ZrO₂ results using titanium it is necessary to change parameters, especially powder feeding rate

and energy density. The authors compared selected samples with traditional for electric machines magnet coating Ni-Cu-Ni and without any cover. The laboratory tests confirmed an increase resistance to external conditions.

Carrying out the above-described basic research on surface-modified neodymium magnets is an important issue from the point of view of the development of scientific disciplines such as electrical engineering, materials engineering or chemical and mechanical engineering, and will allow us to explore the issue of innovative solutions with high potential in the context of measuring up to modern challenges posed to the areas of efficient energy extraction and utilization.

A detailed study of neodymium magnets surface-modified with Ti and ZrO₂ will make it possible to design a machine with magnets resistant to water (including seawater) and high temperatures. Such machines will be able to be successfully used not only in cooperation with renewable energy sources, but also, for example, in the marine industry, where the resistance of devices to salt water is an important aspect, or in mining, where temperature resistance is extremely important. Further study will focus on more detailed study on structural changes after laser-assisted cladding with different powders.

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5. References

- [1] A. Saadoun and Y. Amirat, Magnetic flux density measurement in permanent magnet synchronous machines," 2014 15th International Conference on Sciences and Techniques of Automatic Control and Computer Engineering (STA), Hammamet, Tunisia (2014) 355-359, Doi: 10.1109/STA.2014.7086693.
- [2] N. Radwan-Pragłowska, T. Węgiel, Permanent Magnet Selections for AFPM Disc Generators, *Energies* 15 (2022) 7601. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15207601>
- [3] H. Nagata, Y. Shingaki, Coating method and apparatus, a permanent magnet, and manufacturing method thereof, Patent: US8771422B2, 2014, License USPTO TOS
- [4] S. Constantinides, Modern Permanent Magnets, Chapter 11 - Permanent magnet coatings and testing procedures, *Electronic and Optical Materials, Modern Permanent Magnets*, Woodhead Publishing (2022) 371-402. Doi:10.1016/B978-0-323-88658-1.00011-X
- [5] C. W. Cheng, H. C. Man and F. T. Cheng, Magnetic and corrosion characteristics of Nd-Fe-B magnet with various surface coatings, *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, 33 (1997) 3910-3912. SoI: 10.1109/20.619612.
- [6] E. Celik, I. H. Mutlu and Y. S. Hascicek, Electrical properties of high temperature insulation coatings by the sol-gel method for magnet technology, *IEEE Transactions on Applied Superconductivity*, 10 (2000) 1341-1344. SoI: 10.1109/77.828484.
- [7] C. Chen, M. H. Walmer and S. Liu, Thermal stability and the effectiveness of coatings for Sm-Co 2 : 17 high-temperature magnets at temperatures up to 550/spl deg/C, *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, 40 (2004) 2928-2930. Doi: 10.1109/TMAG.2004.829323.
- [8] B. Lou, K. Yu and M. Wu, "The Study of Electroless Plating of Ni-Cr-P/Ni-P Composite Coating on Sintered Nd-Fe-B Permanent Magnet," 2010 International Conference on Electrical and Control Engineering, Wuhan, China (2010) 4834-4837. Doi: 10.1109/iCECE.2010.1169.
- [9] Zeng, X., Zhu, G., Gao, Z. et al. Surface polishing by industrial robots: a review. *Int J Adv Manuf Technol* (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-023-10887-3>
- [10] Gao, Y., Bai, Y., Zhu, H. et al. Corrosion Resistance, Mechanical and Magnetic Properties of Cold-Sprayed Al Coating on Sintered NdFeB Magnet. *J Therm Spray Tech* 30, 2117–2127 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11666-021-01266-z>
- [11] Steve Constantinides, Chapter 11 - Permanent magnet coatings and testing procedures, In *Woodhead Publishing Series in Electronic and Optical Materials, Modern Permanent Magnets*, Woodhead Publishing, 2022, Pages 371-402, ISBN 9780323886581, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-88658-1.00011-X>.

- [12] Recent research and development status of laser cladding: A review, Lida Zhu, Pengsheng Xue, Qing Lan, Guiru Meng, Yuan Ren, Zhichao Yang, Peihua Xu, Zhe Liu, *Optics & Laser Technology*, 138, 2021, 106915, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optlastec.2021.106915>
- [13] Y. Liu, Y. Ding, L. Yang, R. Sun, T. Zhang, X. Yang, Research and progress of laser cladding on engineering alloys: A review, *Journal of Manufacturing Processes* 66 (2021) 341-363. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmapro.2021.03.061>
- [14] S. Arulvel, D. Dsilva Winfred Rufuss, J. Akshat, J. Kandasamy, M. Singhal, Laser processing techniques for surface property enhancement: Focus on material advancement, *Surfaces and Interfaces*, 42 (2023) 103293. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfin.2023.103293>
- [15] S. Ignat, P. Sallamand, D. Grevey, M. Lambertin, Magnesium alloys laser (Nd:YAG) cladding and alloying with side injection of aluminum powder, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 225 (2004) 124–134. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.2351/1.5060245>
- [16] Z. Ullah Arif, M. Yasir Khalid, E. ur Rehman, S. Ullah, M. Atif, A. Tariq, A review on laser cladding of high-entropy alloys, their recent trends and potential applications, *Journal of Manufacturing Processes*, 68 (2021) 225-273. Doi: [10.1016/j.jmapro.2021.06.041](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmapro.2021.06.041)
- [17] Laser treatment of a neodymium magnet and analysis of surface characteristics, B.S. Yilbas, H. Ali, M. Rizwan, M. Kassas, *Optics & Laser Technology*, 82 (2016) 191-198. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optlastec.2016.03.003>
- [18] J. Liu, H. Yua, C. Chen, F. Weng, J. Dai, Research and development status of laser cladding on magnesium alloys: A Review, *Opt. Las. Eng., Opt. Las. Eng.* 93 (2017) 195–210. Doi: [10.1016/j.optlaseng.2017.02.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optlaseng.2017.02.007)
- [19] Y. Guo, Y. Zhang, Z. Li, S. Wei, T. Zhang, L. Yang, S. Liu, Microstructure and properties of in-situ synthesized ZrC-Al₃Zr reinforced composite coating on AZ91D magnesium alloy by laser cladding, *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 334 (2018) 471–478. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2633366X20906160>
- [20] C. Wang, J. Li, T. Wang, L. Chai, C. Deng, Y. Wang, Y. Huang, Microstructure and properties of pure titanium coating on Ti-6Al-4V alloy by laser cladding, *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 416 (2021) 127137. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2021.127137>
- [21] Y. Gong, M. Wu, X. Miao, C. Cui, Effect of CeO₂ on crack sensitivity and tribological properties of Ni60A coatings prepared by laser cladding, *Adv. Mech. Eng.* 13 (4) (2021) 1–12. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/16878140211013125>
- [22] O.S. Fatoba, E.T. Akinlabi, S.A. Akinlabi, S. Krishna, Influence of Rapid Solidification and Optimized Laser Parameters Relationship on the Geometrical and Hardness Properties of Ti- Al-Cu Coatings, *Mater. Today.: Proc.* 18 (2019) 2859–2867. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2019.07.153>

- [23] A. Pizzatto, M. Felipe, Teixeira, A. Rabelo, T. Falcade, A. Scheid, Microstructure and Wear Behaviour of NbC-Reinforced Ni-Based Alloy Composite Coatings by Laser Cladding, *Mater. Res.* 24 (2021) e. 20200447. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1980-5373-MR-2020-0447>
- [24] S. Reda, A. Ali, A. Hamid, A. Hussein, A. Nofal, S. Ibrahim, H. Elnaby, H. Elgazzar, A contribution to laser cladding of Ti-6Al-4V titanium alloy, *Metall. Res. Technol.* 116 (2019) 634. Doi: [10.1051/metal/2019060](https://doi.org/10.1051/metal/2019060)
- [25] M. B. Rodrigues, R. G. N. Silva, M. Pereira, R. H. Gonçalves e Silva and E. W. Teichmann, Effect of dynamic wire feeding on deposition quality in laser cladding process, *J. Laser Appl.* 32 (2020) 022065. Doi: [10.2351/7.0000097](https://doi.org/10.2351/7.0000097).
- [26] A. Riquelme, P. Rodrigo, M. D. Escalera-Rodríguez, J. Rams, Characterisation and mechanical properties of Al/SiC metal matrix composite coatings formed on ZE41 magnesium alloys by laser cladding, *Res. Phys.* 13 (2019) 102160. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rinp.2019.102160>
- [27] J. D. Majumdar, I. Manna, Mechanical properties of a laser-surface-alloyed magnesium-based alloy (AZ91) with nickel, *Scr. Mater.* 62 (2010) 579–581. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0031918X14130122>
- [28] Z. Mei, L.F. Guo, T.M. Yue, The effect of laser cladding on the corrosion resistance of magnesium ZK60/SiC composite, *J. Mater. Process. Technol.* 161 (2005) 462–466. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2004.07.084>
- [29] C. Tan, H. Zhu, T. Kuang, J. Shi, H. Liu, Z. Liu, Laser cladding Al-based amorphous-nanocrystalline composite coatings on AZ80 magnesium alloy under water cooling condition, *J. Alloy. Compd.* 690 (2017) 108–115. Doi: [10.1016/j.jallcom.2016.08.082](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2016.08.082)
- [30] A. Dziadoń, R. Mola, L. Błaz, The microstructure of the surface layer of magnesium laser alloyed with aluminum and silicon, *Mater. Charact.* 118 (2016) 505–513. Doi: [10.1016/j.matchar.2016.06.034](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchar.2016.06.034)
- [31] Y. Yang, H. Wu, Improving the wear resistance of AZ91D magnesium alloys by laser cladding with Al–Si powders, *Mater. Lett.* 63 (2009) 19–21. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2008.08.026>
- [32] G. Meng, T.M. Yue, X. Lin, H. Yang, H. Xie, X. Ding, Laser surface forming of AlCoCrCuFeNi particle reinforced AZ91D matrix composites, *Opt. Laser Technol.* 70 (2015) 119–127. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optlastec.2015.02.001>
- [33] T.M. Yue, H. Xie, X. Lin, b.H.O. Yang, G.H. Meng, Solidification behavior in laser cladding of AlCoCrCuFeNi high-entropy alloy on magnesium substrates, *J. Alloy. Compd.* 587 (2014) 588–593. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2013.10.254>
- [34] S. Gao, H. Liao, X. Yan, Y. Yang, J. Wang, C. Chang, Q. Chu, Z. Deng, B. Lu, M. Liu, N. Fenineche, Effects of heat treatment on the microstructures and magnetic properties of selective laser melted Fe-3 wt%Si functional soft magnet, *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 951 (2023) 169840. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2023.169840>

[35] J. Wu, N. T. Aboulkhair, S. Robertson, Z. Zhou, P.A.J. Bagot, M. P. Moody, M. Degano, I. Ashcroft, R.J.M. Hague, Amorphous-crystalline nanostructured Nd-Fe-B permanent magnets using laser powder bed fusion: Metallurgy and magnetic properties, *Acta Materialia*, 259 (2023) 119239. Doi: [10.1016/j.actamat.2023.119239](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2023.119239)

[36] O. Tosoni, E. B. Mendonça, J. Reijonen, A. Antikainen, L. Schäfer, S. Riegg, O. Gutfleisch, High-coercivity copper-rich Nd-Fe-B magnets by powder bed fusion using laser beam method, *Additive Manufacturing*, 64 (2023) 103426 Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2023.103426>

[37] W.-Y. Jhang Jian, C.-W. Cheng, W.-C. Chang, T.-Y. Huang, Y.-C. Liang, A.-C. Lee, T.-W. Chang, M.-C. Tsai, Fabrication of crack-free Nd-Fe-B magnets with laser powder bed fusion, *Materialia*, 21 (2022) 101351. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtla.2022.101351>

[38] K.-S. Yu, C.-W. Cheng, A.-C. Lee, W.-Y. Jhang Jian, W.-C. Chang, T.-W. Chang, M. C. Tsai, Additive manufacturing of NdFeB magnets by synchronized three-beam laser powder bed fusion, *Optics & Laser Technology*, 146 (2022) 107604. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optlastec.2021.107604>